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Underdiagnosed obstructive sleep apnea detected by respiratory polygraphy in hospitalized patients with heart failure at a tertiary hospital in Lima-Peru

Subdiagnóstico de apnea obstructiva del sueño detectada mediante la poligrafía respiratoria en pacientes hospitalizados por insuficiencia cardíaca en un hospital de tercer nivel en Lima-Perú

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ABSTRACT

Background: Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA) is often undiagnosed in heart failure (HF) patients. Early identification using affordable sleep studies could improve patient outcomes in resource-limited clinical settings like Peru. The objective was to determine the frequency of OSA in hospitalized HF patients using respiratory polygraphy (RP) (Sleep Study Type III). **Materials and methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted. We included patients >18 years, hospitalized with exacerbated HF, and a STOP-BANG score ≥ 3 . Enrolled patients underwent overnight RP using ApneaLink Air™. Data collected included clinical parameters, the Epworth Sleepiness Scale, and echocardiography results. Statistical analysis was carried out using R Studio. **Results:** Of 46 enrolled patients, 39 underwent successful RP; 84.61% were diagnosed with OSA. Patients exhibited a mean Apnea-Hypopnea Index (AHI) of $14.41 \pm 10.08/h$ with mild (51.28%), moderate (25.64%), and severe (7.69%) cases. Symptoms associated with OSA included a lack of restorative sleep and concentration problems. RP data showed a mean minimum SpO₂ of $76.85 \pm 9.99\%$ and an Oxygen Desaturation Index (ODI) of 20.01 ± 10.66 . Correlation analysis indicated a strong positive correlation between AHI and ODI ($r = 0.73, p < 0.001$) and a moderate negative correlation between AHI and LVEF ($r = -0.64, p = 0.056$). **Conclusion:** This study reveals a high frequency of previously undiagnosed OSA among hospitalized heart failure patients in our institution, indicating the importance of active screening in this high-risk population.

Keywords: Sleep Apnea Syndromes; Heart Failure; Monitoring, Sleep; Peru (Source: MeSH-NLM).

RESUMEN

Introducción: La apnea obstructiva del sueño (AOS) a menudo no se diagnostica en pacientes con insuficiencia cardíaca (IC). La identificación temprana mediante estudios del sueño accesibles podría mejorar los resultados clínicos en entornos con recursos limitados, como Perú. El objetivo fue evaluar la frecuencia de AOS en pacientes hospitalizados por IC utilizando poligrafía respiratoria (PR) (Estudio del Sueño Tipo III). **Materiales y métodos:** Estudio transversal. Se incluyeron pacientes mayores de 18 años con IC exacerbada y un puntaje STOP-BANG ≥ 3 . Fueron sometidos a una PR nocturna utilizando ApneaLink Air™. Se recolectaron parámetros clínicos, la escala de somnolencia de Epworth (ESE) y datos de las ecocardiografías. El análisis estadístico se realizó utilizando R Studio. **Resultados:** De 46 pacientes enrolados, 39 se sometieron a una PR exitosa. El 84,61% fue diagnosticado con AOS. El índice de apnea-hipopnea (IAH) medio fue de $14,41 \pm 10,08/h$, con casos leves (51,28%), moderados (25,64%) y severos (7,69%). Los síntomas asociados con AOS incluyeron falta de sueño reparador y problemas de concentración. Los datos de la PR mostraron una saturación promedio de $76,85 \pm 9,99\%$ y un índice de desaturación de oxígeno (IDO) de $20,01 \pm 10,66$. Se determinó una fuerte correlación positiva entre el IAH y el IDO ($r = 0,73$, $p < 0,001$) y una correlación negativa moderada entre el IAH y la FEVI ($r = -0,64$, $p = 0,056$). **Conclusión:** Este estudio resalta una alta frecuencia de AOS entre los pacientes hospitalizados por IC en nuestra institución, enfatizando su relación con síntomas y parámetros cardiovasculares.

Palabras clave: Apnea del Sueño; Insuficiencia Cardíaca; Monitorización del Sueño; Perú (DeCS-BIREME).

INTRODUCTION

Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) is a high-morbidity respiratory disorder characterized by upper airway narrowing that impairs normal ventilation during sleep, according to the American Academy of Sleep Medicine (AASM) guidelines^[1]. A prospective cohort study reported that patients with OSA had a hazard ratio (HR) of 2.24 (95% CI: 1.30–3.86) for stroke or death compared to those without OSA, even after adjusting for confounders such as hypertension, diabetes, and atrial fibrillation. These findings underscore the importance of early recognition and management of OSA, particularly in populations at risk, such as patients with heart failure (HF)^[2].

Various risk factors have been linked to different symptoms of OSA^[3]. Habitual snoring, for instance, is associated with male sex, older age, higher BMI, and higher socioeconomic status. Observed apneas correlate with higher BMI. Excessive daytime sleepiness is more prevalent among females and older adults. A study conducted in Peru revealed that severe OSA is associated with a short face, retrognathia, and retromaxilla^[4]. Screening tools such as STOP-BANG have demonstrated being useful in identifying patients at high risk for OSA^[5].

Regarding confirmatory diagnosis of sleep apnea/hypopnea syndromes, respiratory polygraphy is considered a practical alternative to full polysomnography, maintaining good sensitivity^[6]. Being less extensive than polysomnography, respiratory polygraphy represents a validated, commercial, and cost-effective diagnostic option, particularly suitable for clinical settings with limited resources.

OSA is linked to cardiovascular morbidity and mortality through various mechanisms, including chronic intermittent hypoxia, increased sympathetic activity, endothelial dysfunction,

inflammation, oxidative stress, and metabolic anomalies^[7]. Additionally, studies have consistently shown a moderate to high prevalence of OSA in patients with heart failure (48%, 52.1%, and 82%)^[8-10], an association with lower hemodynamic function^[9], and a negative correlation with Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction (LVEF), peaked troponin, and peaked B-type natriuretic peptide^[11].

In Peru, early studies from 2006 revealed poor physician recognition of OSA-related symptoms such as snoring, somnolence, and apnea episodes^[12]. Subsequent research in three different Peruvian cities revealed a prevalence of 30.2% for snoring, 18.6% for daytime sleepiness, and 20.9% for observed apneas^[3]. A 2020 review estimated that OSA prevalence in Peru was 53.2%, which could represent 6,873,395 people^[13].

OSA underdiagnosis remains a challenge in our country, largely due to the high cost of polysomnography and the limited availability of specialized sleep medicine centers at public healthcare facilities. Hence, there is an urgent need to assess the use of alternative diagnostic methods for OSA, especially in at-risk populations. Consequently, the main objective of this study was to evaluate OSA cases using respiratory polygraphy as a diagnostic tool among patients hospitalized due to heart failure.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This cross-sectional study included HF patients hospitalized at the Medicine Ward of the Hospital Nacional Arzobispo Loayza (HNAL) located in Lima, Peru, between June 2023 and March 2024. Lima is situated 101 meters above sea level. The inclusion criteria were patients older than 18 years, admitted for HF exacerbation, including both new onset and chronic HF (ACC/AHA Stages C and D), and having a STOP-BANG score ≥ 3 . We excluded patients with

previous diagnoses of OSA and those who rejected or did not provide informed consent.

The attending physicians and research medical team identified patients who were medically stable, required no oxygen support, and were close to discharge. The included patients underwent overnight respiratory polygraphy monitoring. A respiratory polygraphy device, ApneaLink Air™ (ResMed), was used. This is an affordable type 3 home sleep device, already validated and routinely employed for OSA diagnosis at home. This device is capable of measuring five channels of information: respiratory effort, pulse, oxygen saturation (SpO₂%), nasal airflow, and snoring. A micropore tape (3M Micropore) was used to affix the air cannula and oximetry probe to the cheek and hands to minimize the risk of signal loss.

Usually, sleep studies are conducted 24 or 48 hours prior to discharge. The diagnostic studies start approximately at the time the patient falls asleep (around 10-11 PM) and finish around 6-7 AM the following morning. The medical research team supervised the accuracy of the overnight study, and once the patient awakened, the portable device was removed. The polygraphy studies did not delay the planned patient discharge. A minimum of 4 hours of monitoring and recording of all parameters was required to be considered a successful technical study. The data from ApneaLink Air™ was uploaded to the ResMed cloud. The interpretation of the results was carried out by a sleep medicine physician certified by the American Board of Sleep Medicine in a blind manner. For diagnostic purposes, the apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) was used to establish the severity of obstructive sleep apnea, as follows: none (<5 events/hour), mild (5-14.9 events/hour), moderate (15-29.9 events/hour), and severe (≥30 events/hour). Events taken into account included snoring, fatigue, excessive daytime sleepiness, observed episodes of stopped breathing during sleep, waking during the night and gasping or choking, insomnia, nocturia, mouth dryness, morning headaches, concentration problems, and lack of restorative sleep.

Additionally, baseline clinical and demographic data were collected, as well as the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS) and echocardiography results. The ESS is a questionnaire used to assess daytime sleepiness. It consists of eight questions, each asking participants to rate their likelihood of falling asleep in different situations. The score ranges from 0 to 24 points and has been widely validated^[14]. All statistical analyses were performed using R Studio Team 4.4.1 (Boston, USA). Continuous variables were described using the mean and standard deviation. Normal distribution was assessed using histograms and quantile-quantile plots. We used percentages and frequencies for categorical data. The Kruskal-Wallis test was used to compare non-normally distributed variables. Spearman correlation was utilized to evaluate the relationship between AHI and the respiratory polygraphy parameters. P-values ≤0.05 were considered statistically significant.

This study was reviewed and approved by the HNAL Institutional Review Board (#018-2023). All clinical data were anonymized

through coding, ensuring patient confidentiality. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before enrollment. When a patient could not provide a signature, fingerprints were used, or their legal guardian signed for them. It is important to note that the ApneaLink Air™ device used in the study did not pose any harm to patients, aside from minor discomfort in the finger due to the overnight use of the pulse oximeter. All patients received their diagnostic results along with verbal and written recommendations for management. In the final medical report, we also included treatment suggestions such as initiating CPAP or mandibular advancement devices when appropriate.

RESULTS

We enrolled a total of 46 patients; 39 underwent successful overnight polygraphic respiratory monitoring (>4h of recording). The mean time recorded was 7 hours and 25 minutes ± 48 minutes. Of the 39 patients included, 14 were men and 25 were women (mean age 62.3±13.73). Heart failure etiology was categorized as valvular (33.33%), hypertensive (25.64%), arrhythmic (17.94%), ischemic (10.25%), myocardial (10.25%), and interventricular communication (IVC) (2.56%). We found type 2 diabetes mellitus in 64.10% of the patients, hypertension in 53.84%, and metabolic syndrome criteria in 15.84%. Table 1 summarizes the overall clinical characteristics. Among the 39 patients, 23 claimed they were hospitalized due to HF for the first time, 11 for the second time, 3 for the third time, and 2 for the fourth time.

Table 1. Clinical Characteristics of Heart Failure Patients.

Characteristic	N (%) or \bar{X}
Age	62.3
Sex	
Female	25 (64%)
Male	14 (36%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.71
HTN	21 (53.8%)
T2DM	25 (64.1%)
Metabolic Syndrome	6 (15.8%)
Snoring	23 (59%)
ESS	
Normal Sleepiness <10	29 (74.4%)
Excessive Sleepiness	10 (25.6%)
ProBNP (pg/mL)	1962.83
HF etiology	
Valvular	13 (33.3%)
Hypertensive	10 (25.6%)
Arrhythmic	7 (17.9%)
Ischemic	4 (10.3%)
Myocardial	4 (10.3%)
IVC	1 (2.6%)

The mean neck circumference was 38.69 ± 7.08 cm, with a range from 13.3 to 60 cm. Participants also had a mean waist circumference of 96.83 ± 19.65 cm. The mean Body Mass Index (BMI) was 26.67 ± 6.37 , ranging from 16.65 to 43.56 kg/cm^2 . According to BMI, patients were classified as underweight (3.03%), normal (45%), overweight (27.27%), type 1 obesity (12.12%), type 2 obesity (9.09%), and morbid obesity (3.03%). The average ESS score was $7.87 (\pm 5.66)$. In patients with OSA, 69.70% had normal sleepiness, 18.18% had moderate/excessive sleepiness, and 12.12% had severe excessive sleepiness.

The diagnosis of OSA was defined as $\text{AHI} \geq 5$ events/h detected by respiratory polygraphy. The overall OSA frequency was 84.61% in heart failure inpatients: 33 of 39 patients had an $\text{AHI} \geq 5$ events/h (mean 14.41 ± 10.08 /h). Of them, 20 patients were classified as mild OSA ($\text{AHI} 5\text{-}15$ /h), 10 as moderate ($\text{AHI} >15$ /h), and 3 as severe ($\text{AHI} >30$ /h). The mean minimum pulse was 52.88 ± 11.02 ; the average minimum oxygen saturation was $76.85 \pm 9.99\%$; and the mean ODI was 20.01 ± 10.66 . Central apnea (Cheyne-Stokes respiration) was found in 30.30% of patients. 69.70% showed

no CSR. Table 2 shows the comparison of clinical and respiratory polygraph data categorized by the AHI index.

Of the 33 HF patients with OSA, 35.89% underwent transthoracic echocardiograms during hospitalization. The Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction (LVEF) average was 63.55%, and only 7.14% presented with reduced LVEF (HFrEF). The probability of pulmonary hypertension was estimated to be high in 14.28% of the patients.

Correlation between the Apnea Hypopnea Index (AHI) and ESS, LVEF, ProBNP, $\text{SpO}_2\%$ (min), $\text{SpO}_2\%$ (Avg), Pulse min, Pulse Avg, and Oxygen Desaturation Index (ODI) was evaluated using Spearman correlational analysis. This showed that AHI was strongly positively correlated with ODI ($r=0.73$, $p<0.001$) and moderately negatively correlated with LVEF ($r=-0.54$, $p=0.056$), but the latter was not statistically significant. The other parameters (ESS, ProBNP, $\text{SpO}_2\%$ (min), $\text{SpO}_2\%$ (Avg), Pulse min, Pulse Avg) showed no correlation with AHI ($r=0.035$, $r=0.22$, $r=0.032$, $r=-0.11$, $r=0.039$, $r=0.008$, respectively).

Table 2. Comparison of clinical and respiratory polygraph data with Apnea-Hypopnea Index of OSA and HF patients.

	5 ≤ AHI < 15 N = 20	15 ≤ AHI < 30, N = 10	AHI ≥ 30, N = 3	*Overall*, N = 33	p-value
BMI	24.6 (20.9, 30.1)	26.1 (24.1, 27.9)	28.8 (25.7, 33.7)	25.5 (21.6, 29.8)	0.594
ESS*					0.302
Normal sleepiness	14 (70%)	8 (80%)	1 (33%)	23 (69.70%)	
Excessive sleepiness	6 (30%)	2 (20%)	2 (67%)	10 (29.3%)	
Neck Circumference	38.5 (35.8, 42.2)	38.0 (36.2, 41.2)	38.0 (36.5, 40.5)	38.0 (36.0, 42.0)	0.979
Waist Circumference	97 (86; 107)	104 (92; 106)	98 (95; 100)	101 (89; 105)	0.892
HF type					0.294
Valvular	9(27.27%)	3(9.09%)	0	12 (36.36%)	
Hypertensive	5(15.15%)	0	3 (9.09%)	8 (24.24%)	
Arrhythmic	3(9.09%)	3 (9.09%)	0	6 (18.18%)	
Ischemic	1(3.03%)	2 (6.06%)	0	3 (9.09%)	
Myocardial	2 (6.06%)	2 (6.06%)	0	4 (12.12%)	
Polygraphy parameters					
$\text{SpO}_2\%$ (min)	82 (67; 85)	77 (74; 84)	74 (71; 77)	80 (70; 84)	0.699
$\text{SpO}_2\%$ (avg)	93.00 (91.75, 94.00)	92.00 (90.00, 93.75)	93.00 (92.00, 93.50)	93.00 (91.00, 94.00)	0.56
Pulse Min	52 (45. 57)	48 (42. 60)	57 (50. 68)	52 (44. 59)	0.685
Pulse (avg)	67 (60. 78)	70 (67. 73)	72 (69. 82)	69 (63. 76)	0.671
ODI**	13 (10. 16)	24 (21. 26)	40 (37. 43)	20 (12. 26)	<0.001

*ESS = Epworth Sleepiness Scale. **ODI = Oxygen Desaturation Index.

DISCUSSION

To our knowledge, this is the first study that evaluated OSA frequency with respiratory polygraphy in hospitalized HF patients in Lima, Peru. The main goal of this study was to determine the frequency of OSA in HF patients, which was found to be 84.3%. This is higher than previous international reports, which a frequency of 70.6% for Sleep-Disordered Breathing (SDB) and 47.6% for OSA [15]. Besides, one study showed 81% of SDB and 54% for OSA [16], while another reported 75.5% for OSA [17]. In the HF patients with OSA, the most common HF etiology was valvular (36.36%), followed by hypertensive (24.24%) and arrhythmic (18.18%). In contrast, another study demonstrated a frequency of 35.9% for ischemic pathology, 17.3% for hypertensive etiology, and a similar frequency of 21.4% for arrhythmic etiology [15].

Echocardiogram results from our study indicated that most of our patients with OSA had a preserved HFpEF (LVEF \geq 50%). Despite our small study sample, this is consistent with reports of 49% OSA prevalence among HFpEF patients [9]. Other studies, using respiratory polygraphy in outpatients, have also found an increased prevalence of OSA (62%) in HFpEF compared to the HFrEF group (18%) [16]. Interestingly, it has been suggested that low LVEF could be an indicator of central apnea [8]. LV diastolic dysfunction, systolic pulmonary artery pressure (sPAP), and the right ventricular internal diameter (RVID) have also been independently associated with OSA severity [18]. Within our study, the Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction (LVEF) negatively correlated with the Apnea-Hypopnea Index, although it was not statistically significant. This finding is consistent with a study in China that reported a correlation of $r=-0.309$, $p<0.001$ [9].

Traditionally, polysomnography has been the gold standard for diagnosing OSA in various clinical settings [19]. However, respiratory polygraphy devices are increasingly being used to diagnose SDB, including OSA [6]. In a large multicenter study, respiratory polygraphy showed a sensitivity of 96% and specificity of 57% for AHI \geq 5, and a sensitivity of 87% and specificity of 86% for AHI >10 [6]. These findings support its utility in detecting moderate-to-severe OSA, especially in resource-limited settings [6]. Another study demonstrated the accuracy of diagnosing OSA among inpatients using respiratory polygraphy compared with polysomnography [17]. Along the same lines, other studies have demonstrated the utility of respiratory polygraphy in inpatient settings [8]. Respiratory polygraphy successfully recognized both obstructive and central sleep apnea in patients with co-morbidities [20]. Similarly, other studies diagnosed OSA in the presence of atrial fibrillation [21].

In our context, compared to high-income countries, we suspect that many cases of OSA passed on underdiagnosed. Despite the high volume of HF patient admissions, physicians often overlook OSA symptoms and do not receive a multidisciplinary OSA assessment. Given the cost-effectiveness and utility of the home study devices, we found a great opportunity to broaden their clinical use [22]. The respiratory polygraph calculated important parameters for further assessing the severity of

OSA. This included the Oxygen Desaturation Index (ODI), which measures the number of times per hour of sleep that a patient's blood oxygen levels drop by at least 3% in blood oxygen saturation [23]. Typically, the ODI correlates with the severity of OSA, as demonstrated here by its positive correlation with the Apnea-Hypopnea Index (AHI). Using retrospective data from polysomnography studies, some researchers have proposed the ODI as an alternative severity parameter to the AHI [24], and even as a diagnostic tool [25]. Other parameters, such as prolonged obstructive respiratory events without severe desaturation, have linked to a higher risk of recurrent cardiovascular events [26].

According to the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS), we found that most of the OSA/HF patients exhibited normal sleepiness (69.70%). This suggests that the ESS may not be suitable for screening OSA in HF patients, and other criteria such as STOP-BANG could be used instead [5].

We observed that most readmissions were first-time occurrences, but some patients were readmitted for the second or even the fourth time. One study estimated the costs of cardiovascular readmissions in patients with heart failure who had sleep-disordered breathing, such as obstructive sleep apnea (OSA). They found that both adjusted and unadjusted readmission costs were almost twice as high among OSA patients [27]. This data suggests the importance of a multidisciplinary approach to care for HF patients to improve patient outcomes and reduce healthcare expenditures.

This study has some limitations. First, some polygraphy readings were excluded due to logistical difficulties, and others due to limited patient health literacy, potentially leading to OSA underestimation. Although the study was conducted at a single center with a small sample and limited access to devices, a high proportion of OSA cases was still identified. It is worth noting that the AHI was manually scored instead of using the automated scoring of the device. Finally, our study population—hospitalized HF patients with elevated OSA risk (STOP-BANG \geq 3)—represents a specific clinical subgroup; thus, the findings should not be generalized to other HF populations or in ambulatory settings without further validation.

Conclusions

The overall frequency of OSA among HF inpatients was 84.3% using respiratory polygraphy in a limited-resource clinical setting. We found that concentration problems and lack of restorative sleep were the most commonly associated symptoms of OSA. The ODI was positively correlated with OSA severity. The utility of respiratory polygraphy in diagnosing OSA, despite its limitations, points to the need for comprehensive screening and multidisciplinary care for HF patients. Future research is encouraged to further address these findings and enhance patient management and follow-up to improve outcomes and reduce healthcare costs.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization DHR, EBL; Design JCH, CRR, NVR; Literature search JCH, CRR, NVR; Resources JCH, PAD, CCG, LNM; Materials PAD, CCG, LNM; Data Collection JCH, CRR, NVR; Processing Analysis and/or Interpretation EBL, PAD, CCG, LNM; Writing-original draft JCH, CRR; Supervision DRH, EBL; Critical review DRH EBL; Writing-Review & Editing PAD, CCG, LNM, EBL, JCH, DRH; Validation DRH, PAD, CCG, LNM.

Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence

The authors declare that they did not use generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools at any stage of the study's development or in the writing of the manuscript. All supporting material appearing in the text (figures or tables, if applicable) was prepared by the authors, without requiring the support of any AI tools.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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